

Articles in German

VOLKER W. THÜREY

Bremen, Germany

Doi <https://doi.org/10.55640/ijssl-06-05-05>

ABSTRACT

Articles 'der, die, das' in the German language are important. Unlike some other languages, there are three grammatical genders of nouns. Fortunately, there are rules, often the ending of a word determines the article.

Keywords: Article; German.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many people learn the German language. Unlike some other languages, German has three different articles: 'der', 'die', and 'das', including 'das' for the neuter gender. Learning the correct article is easy for a child who acquires German as a first language, but it can be difficult for an adult. Fortunately, there are rules, that help you remember which article is correct. One method I know is based on the ending of the noun.

2. THE ENDING

- Nouns with the ending '-ung' are feminine, i.e. they take the article 'die', such as the word 'Entschuldigung' (excuse). Other examples are 'Versuchung' (temptation) and 'Unterstellung' (allegation).
- I have found further patterns that also seem to be rules. I did not find any exception.
- Nouns with the ending '-eit' also are feminine, i.e. they take the article 'die', such as the word 'Krankheit' (illness). Other examples are 'Feigheit' (cowardice), and 'Bescheidenheit' (modesty).
- Nouns with the ending '-ie' are feminine. The syllable 'ie' is pronounced like 'ee'. Examples include 'Melodie' (melody), and 'Symphonie' (symphony).
- Nouns with the ending '-ion' also are feminine. Examples include 'Revolution' (Revolution), and 'Subtraktion' (subtraction).
- Nouns with the ending '-ismus' are masculine, i.e. they take the article 'der', such as the word 'Optimismus' (optimism). Other examples are 'Kapitalismus' (capitalism), and 'Organismus' (Organism).
- Nouns with the ending '-ling' also are masculine, i.e. they take the article 'der', such as the word 'Schmetterling' (butterfly). Other examples are Fiesling (meanie) and 'Feigling' (coward).

Acknowledgement: We thank Bouchra Ben Zahir for the rule and Lydia Ramachandran for a careful reading.